

A discourse-analytical study of the japa phenomenon in Nigerian digital and media narratives

Isaiah ALUYA, Bingham University, Nigeria¹

Nkechinyere U. NWAEGBE, Bingham University, Nigeria

This study analyses discussions on the Nigerian migration trend ‘japa’ to understand how it influences interpretations of citizenship and national identity. The research uses qualitative content analysis to explore 32 comments selected from four tweets by *Punch* Newspapers and *The Vanguard* on X (formerly *Twitter*) between 2022 and 2025, with eight comments per tweet. The study applies Norman Fairclough’s Three-Dimensional Model of Discourse and Theo van Leeuwen’s Social Actor Representation Theory to unpack linguistic, discursive, and social practices in the discourse. Findings reveal that users frame japa as a rational escape from a failing state and a contested moral act with implications for civic duty and legitimacy. Political elites are activated as agents of dysfunction, while youths are passivated as victims or reimagined as active dissenters through decision to emigrate. The study shows that japa functions as a metaphor where Nigerians critique state, negotiate identity, and reimagine citizenship beyond traditional boundaries.

Keywords: Civic Engagement; Critical Discourse; Digital Discourse; Migration; National Identity

1. Introduction

Throughout history, mankind has exercised the essential right to move between different locations. People abandoned their homes to pursue better living conditions, along with accessible healthcare and educational opportunities, and enhanced infrastructure in supportive environments. Nigerian youths are not unique in their mass departure from their hometowns whenever they find an opportunity, as this phenomenon extends beyond Nigeria. However, Yusuf et al. (2023), quoting Aliyu et al. (2018), state that “Nigerians represent one of the most mobile populations in Africa and are found virtually on every continent” (p. 53). Developing countries faced disruptive socio-economic challenges throughout the COVID-19 pandemic,

¹ Corresponding Author: Isaiah.aluya@binghamuni.edu.ng

resulting in a significant increase in the number of their nationals seeking better opportunities abroad afterwards. The Yoruba word ‘japa’ has become a sociolinguistic term used to express both the situation of Nigeria and the experiences of its citizens. As cited in Adeniji et al. (2024), the word *japa* is “frequently used playfully or informally and has taken on a life of its own in modern Nigerian youth culture” (p. 1).

Japa, as Falola (2022) puts it, “does not mean to walk away. It is to flee from danger or a compromising situation . . . an abusive relationship, an extremely demanding situation, and life-threatening issues. And the king of the meanings: Flee from Nigeria” (p. 1). In his article titled ‘Japa’, he sums up that Nigerian society has reached a point where unnecessary compromises and prolonged discomfort cannot be endured any further. However, he also cautions that “all Nigerians cannot leave,” which places the responsibility of taking on the roles of citizenship on the people. The question is, how? The japa phenomenon emerges from socio-economic (Ayanwale, 2024) and political (Liu, 2024) challenges and is mediated in digital discourse, where it receives both celebration and critique while gaining new interpretations through social commentary.

In his article titled “How ‘japa’ became the Nigerian buzzword for emigration,” Dayo (2022, p. 1) states that “japa has gained cultural momentum” with the help of young Nigerians. In his view, japa is both a disavowal of patriotism and a new cultural personality. Tweets about japa continue to surge, with both older adults and young people leaving Nigeria because they believe the diaspora offers them the best opportunity to succeed. Since the 1980s, political instability and unfavorable conditions have driven the country’s emigration rates upward, while data collection has expanded to track this increase. Nigeria has experienced a negative migration balance since the beginning of the 21st century, and, as of 2021, migration rate statistics show that more people are leaving than entering the country. The contemporary discourse surrounding Nigerian migration, popularly encapsulated in the Yoruba term japa, has transcended policy debates to become a socio-political phenomenon deeply entangled in questions of governance, identity, and legitimacy.

Although scholars have investigated the japa phenomenon, much of the literature has largely focused on its socio-economic and political dimensions. Little or no scholarly attention has been paid to exploring how japa functions and is debated in digital media as a cultural metaphor and identity marker. This gap is what this study seeks to address from a critical discourse-analytical perspective, to reveal how the language of media texts and social media engagements on japa discourse interrogates citizenship by and for migrants.

The aim of this study is to examine how the digital discourse surrounding the japa phenomenon redefines the idea of citizenship and national belonging in

Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks (1) to analyse the linguistic and discursive strategies deployed by Nigerian *X* (formerly *Twitter*) users on digital platforms, particularly *X*, to construct the japa narrative; (2) to investigate how various social actors are represented, activated, or excluded in digital discourse on japa; and (3) to explore how the japa discourse in digital spaces reconstructs the understanding of Nigerian citizenship, identity, and national belonging, especially among young people. In line with these objectives, the study is guided by the following research questions:

- (1) What linguistic and discursive strategies are used by Nigerian digital users, particularly on *X*, to construct the japa narrative?
- (2) How are social actors represented, activated, or excluded in japa-related digital discourse?
- (3) In what ways does the japa discourse in digital spaces reshape the idea of Nigerian citizenship, identity, and national belonging from the perspective of youth migration?

This study contributes to migration discourse, digital sociolinguistics, and citizenship studies by unpacking how everyday Nigerians are reframing belonging in a globalised world. It provides a linguistic and cultural lens through which diaspora nationalism and youth political disengagement can be understood. By focusing on how ‘japa’ is discussed, imagined, and mobilised in digital spaces such as *X*, the study offers an original contribution to existing knowledge from the perspective of a discourse-theoretical reimagining of Nigerian citizenship in the age of migration.

2. Background

Although people increasingly use the term ‘japa’ to describe specific social realities in Nigeria, scholars have conducted limited research on how this phenomenon changes ideas of citizenship and national identity within Nigeria’s socio-political conversations. Multiple disciplines have studied Nigerian migration through the lens of the japa syndrome, including science and technology, as seen in works by Andrew and Ntaka-Joshua (2025) and Adeniji et al. (2024); political science and philosophy, through Liu (2024), Okunade and Awosusi (2023), Nwobodo (2024), and Afunugo (2023); law, with contributions from Uwakwe (2024); social sciences, by Ayanwale (2024) and Mpigi (2023); anthropology, as studied by Liu (2023); media and communication studies, by Adegoke (2023); and environmental studies, as discussed by Yusuf et al. (2023), to mention a few. Research focusing on this phenomenon from a linguistic perspective remains scarce or non-existent.

This review section examines existing scholarly interventions to determine the socio-political, ideological, and symbolic constructions of ‘japa’ through the

perspective provided by Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). Andrew and Ntaka-Joshua's (2025) research examines the impact of japa on scientific and technological fields, demonstrating that brain drain causes industrial stagnation and ineffective policies. Similarly, Adeniji et al. (2024) present a distinctive and technically rigorous research contribution that models japa through a mathematical framework. The analysis of brain drain, emigration, and return migration dynamics becomes possible when researchers develop a 'japa model' through a system of non-linear differential equations using data from over ten years.

The study by Ayanwale (2024) uses constructivist theory to examine how socio-economic elements shape Nigerian migration trends towards Japan. He conceptualises japa as a social construct responding to Nigeria's systemic failures, while migrants use education as a means to facilitate their departure instead of pursuing it as an objective. Uwakwe (2024) examines human rights issues within the migration trend by showing how economic and social rights violations among Nigerian youth create a dual migration motive of escape and dignity search. Uwakwe's doctrinal approach intersects with Ayanwale's findings by depicting migration as a reaction to socio-political collapse.

Liu's (2023) anthropological study uses narrative interviews to produce an in-depth cultural analysis of the japa phenomenon among Nigeria's middle-class and youth populations. Liu describes japa as a manifestation of existential urgency. The analysis demonstrates the pressing need for Nigerian youth to leave their country and challenges traditional survival migration concepts by showing that Nigerians move because of extended structural hardships rather than immediate threats.

Adegoke (2023) examines how media technologies and platforms shape migration discussions by demonstrating social media's function in spreading information, forming support networks, and constructing migration-related narratives. The research shows that platforms such as *WhatsApp* and *YouTube* do not initiate migration but play a crucial role in shaping how people prepare for and understand their departure process. That study shares similarity with the present study in examining digital platforms as a forum where concepts of citizenship and belonging are redefined; however, the current research is grounded in CDA, unlike Adegoke's study.

Mpigi's (2023) study investigates the influence of japa on Nigerian individuals by focusing on its impact within religious communities. The research shows that migration leads to shortages in religious leadership and disrupts the continuity of church operations. It also recognises how the worldwide expansion of Nigerian Christianity represents a potential positive outcome. These studies establish significant context that helps to explain japa as both a

youth movement and a force reshaping institutional dynamics and national capabilities.

Afunugo's (2023) work complements Mpigi's study by integrating Stewardship Theory with African communal values from a philosophical and ethical perspective. The work focuses on normative aspects while identifying migration as a phenomenon that requires moral renewal, governance reform, and community-based solidarity to address it, positioning 'japa' as a dual crisis encompassing both moral and economic dimensions.

Okunade and Awosusi (2023) examine the japa syndrome through an empirical analysis of Nigerian migration patterns to the United Kingdom. The study approaches the issue through three interconnected perspectives, including globalisation, neoliberal policies, and fragile state apparatuses. The research shows that numerous Nigerian migrants deliberately obtain study visas to escape systemic stagnation rather than to pursue genuine academic goals. Their work shares thematic connections with Liu (2024, 2023) and Uwakwe (2024), while relying more heavily on interview data. The study identifies citizenship as an instrumental discourse that evolves through changing connections among mobility rights, legal frameworks, and survival strategies.

Nwobodo's (2024) study, *Japa pandemic: Battling for the souls of Nigerian youths*, presents a critical philosophical analysis of japa, which it identifies as a pandemic stemming from poor governance and leadership failures. The research uses secondary data analysis, alongside a thorough review of existing literature, to argue that the spread of the japa phenomenon constitutes a pandemic.

Yusuf et al. (2023) explore the mass emigration of youth through both demographic and environmental perspectives to determine influencing factors. Through a descriptive survey research methodology, the study examines the youth population of Osun State to demonstrate how migration decisions are affected by insecurity, unemployment, and infrastructure deficiencies. The study also examines gender-specific views on migration to show how men and women have different migration motivations.

Collectively, these studies establish a strong interdisciplinary basis for comprehending the japa syndrome. They present migration as a complex reaction to profound structural problems while demonstrating differences in their methodologies and theoretical approaches. However, the reviewed literature primarily examines the push-and-pull effects of the japa syndrome but ignores how language shapes civic engagement and national identity in Nigeria. They also lack the explicit use of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), which creates a substantial research gap that the current study aims to fill.

This study utilises Fairclough's three-dimensional framework to examine the interactions among text, discursive practice, and social practice, while integrating van Leeuwen's Social Actor Theory to demonstrate how digital narratives about japa both influence and are influenced by ideological contestations surrounding identity formation and national belonging.

3. Method

This study is hinged on Fairclough's Three-Dimensional Model of Discourse Analysis, as well as aspects of Theo van Leeuwen's Social Actor Representation Theory, as the overarching frameworks for data analysis. Norman Fairclough (1992) defines discourse as a social activity that exists in a dialectical relationship with other aspects of society. His three-dimensional framework analyses discursive events as occurring simultaneously in three dimensions: (a) text, (b) discursive practice, and (c) social practice. The text dimension focuses on the language framework, including vocabulary choices, grammatical structures, and cohesive devices that organise the text. The discursive practice dimension involves the production, distribution, and consumption of texts, including intertextuality and interpretative conventions. The social practice dimension situates discourse within broader ideological and institutional contexts, where power relations shape and are shaped by discourse. According to Fairclough, this framework integrates linguistic analysis with social and political thought for investigating discourse and social change (Fairclough, 1992).

This study also adapts aspects of Theo van Leeuwen's (1996, 2008) Social Actor Representation Theory to extend Fairclough's framework, particularly at the textual and discursive levels, by providing analytical tools for identifying how individuals and groups are represented within discourse. Van Leeuwen outlines several discursive strategies, including (a) 'inclusion' versus 'exclusion', (b) 'activation' versus 'passivation', (c) 'genericisation' versus 'specification', (d) 'nomination' versus 'categorisation', (e) 'assimilation', and (f) 'appraisal'. This study adopts selected categories—namely inclusion and exclusion, activation and passivation, and role allocation—to demonstrate how discursive choices construct social identities and roles that often carry ideological meanings. The study adopts qualitative content analysis as its research design because it supports the subjective interpretation of textual data.

3.1. Participants

The participants in this study consist of users on X (formerly *Twitter*) who engaged with selected tweets related to the japa phenomenon. A total of 32 responses/comments were purposively sampled from four selected tweets,

with eight comments drawn from each tweet. These responses represent a range of public opinions expressed by individuals engaging with migration discourse in Nigeria.

3.2. Materials

The data for the study were generated from discursive threads of four purposively selected news items posted by *Punch Newspapers* (@MobilePunch) and *The Vanguard* (@vanguardngrnews) on X that discuss migration using the hashtag #japa. The first two tweets, titled “Western nations encouraging japa, granting young Nigerians visas wicked” - Ex-Gov Amosun and “President Bola Tinubu has assured Nigerians that his administration’s economic reforms will encourage professionals who left the country in search of better opportunities to return,” were published by @MobilePunch on 15 October 2022 and 11 March 2025, respectively. Both tweets focus on government actors and elites and garnered 677 and 64 user engagements, respectively. The third and fourth tweets, titled “Japa: No future in Nigeria, nothing’ll make us return - UK-based couple” and “Japa: Leaving family behind was hard, but I had to go where things work - UK-based Nigerian,” were posted by @vanguardngrnews and focus on migration narratives through interviews with Nigerians based abroad. These were published on 27 November 2024 and 25 April 2025, with 165 and 16 user comments, respectively.

3.3. Procedure

Purposive sampling was used to select tweets on X with high engagement or thematic relevance between 2022 and 2025. From the four selected posts, 32 responses were sampled, with equal representation across the two newspapers. *Punch Newspapers* and *The Vanguard* were selected because they are among Nigeria’s leading news outlets with official X handles, and their platforms attract substantial public engagement and diverse opinions on migration and governance issues. Their consistent coverage of japa-related topics makes them valuable sources for discourse analysis. While *Punch* maintains a critical tone, *Vanguard* adopts a more populist style; together, they provide complementary perspectives that strengthen the study. X was selected as the digital platform due to its high level of user engagement and its capacity to provide a rich, real-time representation of public discourse. The extracted tweets are presented in their original form without modification or refinement.

4. Results

This section provides a detailed analysis of the study data. The analysis deploys Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) as its theoretical framework to examine

selected responses by users on *X*, to reveal the linguistic and discursive strategies used to interpret the *japa* phenomenon.

Tweet 1: “Western nations encouraging *japa*, granting young Nigerians visas wicked - Ex-Gov Amosun

Comment 1: “Says a man who schooled at University of Westminster, whose children were born and are based abroad . . .” (@MobilePunch)

Comment 2: “By the way, where is Sen. Amosun family now? How long have they been abroad this year alone?” (@MobilePunch)

The above comments, which are reactions to the first tweet, highlight political hypocrisy and elite privilege. The textual analysis reveals an interrogative and accusatory tone, highlighting contradictions between public statements and private actions. The discursive practice dimension draws on shared public memory of elite hypocrisy, while social practices relate to Nigeria’s political class benefiting from foreign systems they publicly criticize. Van Leeuwen’s framework identifies exclusion of the elite’s own migration from the discourse (“passivation”), while commenters activate elite actors as actively making choices that undermine their own statements.

Comment 3: “What is wicked is politicians like U stealing the county's wealth and using it for your personal needs, instead of using the wealth to develop the country and create more jobs.” (@MobilePunch)

Comment 4: “The wickedness is you corrupt politicians not using Nigeria money to make the country comfortable . . .” (@MobilePunch)

The lexical choices (e.g., stealing, corrupt, wicked, wickedness) foreground moral condemnation. This is a critique of institutional failure using highly evaluative language. At the discursive practice level, the comments invoke a citizen vs. state dichotomy, constructing a collective “we” who suffer, and a corrupt “they” who exploit. Exploring van Leeuwen’s role allocation politicians are activated as agents of decay, while citizens are passivated—portrayed as victims. These role assignments expose the inequitable distribution of responsibility and accountability in public discourse.

Comment 5: “Embassies give visas to applicants alone. And if Nigeria is good, no one will want to Japa.” (@MobilePunch)

Comment 6: “You should encourage your citizens to stay back with good governance.” (@MobilePunch)

The comments above discursively reframed migration as a right and rational act, rather than betrayal or loss. Fairclough's approach helps show how this counter-discourse resists the original framing of migration as "wicked." The social practice layer reflects broader global dynamics of labour mobility and failed nationhood ("And if Nigeria is good, no one will want to Japa," ". . . encourage your citizens to stay back with good governance"). The commenters re-evaluate the morality of migration, aligning it with self-preservation, survival, and agency, thus legitimating 'japa' as citizenship in action.

Comment 7: "I don't blame him for his ridiculous comments. I blame the interviewer for the failure to ask a follow-up question on what had Amosun done to stem such emigration while serving as a governor." (@MobilePunch)

Comment 8: "You don't want western nation to attract your people yet all you politicians do is impoverish the lives of your people" (@MobilePunch)

These responses above show democratic disillusionment. Citizens see media, ("I blame the interviewer") and state actors represented by "Amosun," as co-conspirators in deflection and deception. These comments attempt to reconstruct power relations, questioning not only political leaders but also the media as gatekeepers of truth. Van Leeuwen's legitimation strategies are inverted—rather than justify Amosun's comments, commenters delegitimize them through rationalisation ("what did he do while in office?"), and authorisation is withdrawn ("you're wickedness itself").

Tweet 2: "President Bola Tinubu has assured Nigerians that his administration's economic reforms will encourage professional who left the country in search of better opportunities to return."

Comment 9: "Tinubu cannot bring back millions of Nigerians who died as a result of his bad economic policy. Tinubu cannot bring back over 7 million business he destroyed in the last two years." (@MobilePunch)

Comment 10: "So, Tinubu thinks his woeful economic policy disasters are working?" (@MobilePunch)

Comment 11: "The administration that failed to build people in the country how is it going to attract people leaving outside the country?" (@MobilePunch)

In response to President Bola Tinubu's speech published in *Punch* Newspapers of 11 March 2025, asserting that his economic reforms will entice diasporic

professionals to return, user comments on post reflect deep scepticism, anger, and disillusionment. The comments above undermine the credibility of the president's economic reforms by pointing to their perceived ineffectiveness. At the textual level, these comments use declarative and rhetorical forms to assert a definitive rejection of the president's promise as exemplified in comment 9 (declarative) and comments 10 and 11 (rhetoric). Phrasal structures like "millions of Nigerians who died," and "woeful economic policy" are deployed to construct a counter-narrative of irreversibility and futility, signalling a loss of faith in recovery. Within Fairclough's discursive practice, these reactions draw on shared intertextual knowledge—previous economic instability, inflation, insecurity—to produce a collective discourse that normalises despair and rejection.

The president, as a social actor, is consistently activated as a destructive agent that "destroyed," and "failed" the citizens, while victims "Nigerians," "businesses" are passivated, rendered as recipients of harm. This role allocation amplifies blame attribution and delegitimises presidential authority.

Comment 12: "We shall see the stars at noon if they come back here nigeria where we are being led like animals! By barbarian style of leadership!" (@MobilePunch)

Comment 13: "Those in Nigeria want to check out. Does he think diasporians who have witnessed what a sane, working society looks like will come back to his policy disasters?" (@MobilePunch)

The above comments reveal that for many Nigerians, emigration (japa) is not just an economic choice but an existential escape from oppression, presenting migration as a rational and moral response to systemic decay. In textual terms, metaphors like "led like animals," "barbarian style of leadership," "stars at noon") characterise state failure. They construct Nigeria as uninhabitable as compared to functional West ("sane, working society"). From a discursive practice angle, users tap into global migratory discourses and contrast the Nigerian state with diasporic experience to assert migration as a form of social critique and resistance. Migration becomes a performative exit that publicly rejects the national contract. Within the social actor model, the government is activated as perpetrators while the youths and emigrants are passivated as the victims. The state, therefore, is stripped of moral legitimacy, and japa is reframed as resistance.

Comment 14: "Assurance no dey buy food for nijeria." (@MobilePunch)

Comment 15: "The newspaper are enabler of bad governance . . . just say he said the sanate said they said the police said. Said said said.

Look at your mates in the abroad. They journalize and report to the citizen." (@MobilePunch)

The comments above demonstrate disillusionment not only with the political class but also with the media, suggesting a collapse in communicative trust as seen in comment 15, "The newspaper are enabler of bad governance." At the textual level, sarcasm and ridicule in "Assurance no dey buy food for nijeria." exemplify rhetoric. The ironic comparison of *Punch* Newspaper with foreign journalism ("look at your mates in the abroad") signals communicative breakdown. The discursive practice reflects the public's alienation from official discourse and mainstream journalism. The *Punch* Newspapers are no longer seen as neutral; rather, they are framed as complicit. This aligns with wider national concerns where citizens question the authenticity and function of news media in authoritarian or semi-authoritarian regimes. From van Leeuwen's perspective, journalists and politicians are activated as agents of misinformation and manipulation. The public, on the other hand, is both included (as knowing observers) and excluded (from meaningful civic engagement), creating a polarised communicative field.

Comment 16: "Who are you working for, Sir, Washington or Brussel? How much more can Nigerians take?" (@MobilePunch)

The above comment expands the discourse beyond national borders, questioning the president's alignment with foreign powers and economic policies. The textual construction "Who are you working for, Sir, Washington or Brussel?" implies that Nigeria's economic suffering is not merely a local issue but entangled in global neo-imperial dynamics. The speaker implies betrayal, suggesting Tinubu's policies serve external interests rather than Nigerians. Discursively, this reflects a growing awareness of how IMF-style reforms or global capital flows affect domestic governance. Postcolonial sovereignty, neoliberal pressures, and elite complicity are foregrounded social practices of mistrust in globalised economic governance. It also repositions the Nigerian leader as a proxy actor for external forces, which raises questions about sovereignty and autonomy. Foreign actors, "Washington or Brussel" are implied agents, and Tinubu is activated as their local executor. The Nigerian populace is passivated, voiceless in economic policymaking.

Tweet 3: Japa: Leaving family behind was hard, but I had to go where things work - UK-based Nigerian

Comment 17: "Very bad decision that you would regret later." (@vanguardngrnews)

Comment 18: "Japa only tells the good sides of the story, not the endless struggles they endure daily." (@vanguardngrnews)

Comment 19: “I am in England as I type this comment, and I sincerely want you to tell me the ‘endless struggles’ . . .” (@vanguardngrnews)

The comments reflect scepticism toward migration, especially positioning it as a short-sighted venture as exemplified by comments 17 and 18. Textually, these comments deploy moralistic language—e.g., “very bad decision,” “regret,” “endless struggles”—which discursively constructs the migrant as naive or short-sighted, and struggling to adapt in a new environment. The omission of systemic push factors such as insecurity or economic instability illustrates exclusion of structural conditions in van Leeuwen’s terms, placing individual responsibility squarely on the migrant. By contrast, comment 19 challenges the view of comment 18 from lived experience. This speaker is activated as a credible social actor anchoring his position in physical and experiential proximity to the UK. Textually, the tone is defensive and interrogative, while discursively, it serves to reframe migration not as abandonment but as a rational and justified decision. This tension between myth and reality of ‘japa’ reflects the contested nature of national allegiance in times of crisis.

Comment 20: “God bless you and guide your family and don’t forget to take them with you when everything soft.” (@vanguardngrnews)

Comment 21: “Very good decision to leave a very corrupt, terrorists ravaged shit hole country to a place where things work for good.” (@vanguardngrnews)

A tone of compassion is evident in comments 20 and 21. They support migration as a survival strategy and wish well for the migrant’s family, evoking affective citizenship. The language of comment 20 is informal and empathetic. It discursively positions the family unit as central to the migrant’s future planning, reinforcing the idea that citizenship extends beyond borders and is negotiated through care and kinship. Unlike it, the tone of comment 21 is highly charged in a total delegitimation of the Nigerian state. It uses ‘profanity’ and absolutes (“shithole,” “very corrupt,” “terrorists ravaged”) to express condemnation (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2015, 2016). The speaker is activated as a judge and witness to the state’s collapse, while Nigeria is passivated and irredeemable. Hope for the Nigerian state is negated, revealing a rupture in the emotional contract of citizenship, where the only rational thing to do is to exit from it. In contrast, the sympathetic framing is challenged by other comments, that rather than share in the enthusiasm of the people leaving the country for greener pastures, evoke a collective guilt and Pan-African disillusionment as seen below:

Comment 22: “Is you and me that will make things work in Nigeria. You left and go to where you will follow the laws that you will not do same in Nigeria. They make their country by staying and fixing thing right not by running away.”

Comment 23: “That’s how we collectively create a mess and run to where there is less mess. We are all unserious. Come and see millions of your pple support failing govts & accept bread for votes. Hungry leaders steal to afford healthcare abroad. It’s all of us, mate. Joke is on the black race.”

Comment 24: “Is very easy to make it outside Nigeria . . . People wey get sense don japa”

Comment 22 positions the migrant as passivated in the act of nation-building, accusing them of hypocrisy. The discursive practice functions as a moral rebuke, “you left,” while others stayed to fix the mess. The speaker in comment 22 emphasises individual failure over systemic critique. Structural causes like corruption, insecurity, bad governance, are excluded while activating the citizen-subject as both law-abiding abroad and lawless at home. Comment 23 reflects a collective introspection in “It’s all of us, mate.” Here, the speaker moves from individual criticism to activation of a collective “we,” shifting the responsibility for national decay from leaders alone to society at large. Textually, the tone is mocking, while discursively, it confronts Nigerian citizen within and outside the country with the paradox of simultaneously enabling and escaping bad governance. This reflects a deeper social practice of internalised disillusionment with the postcolonial African state project, locating failure in both leadership and citizenship. The racial framing “joke is on the black race,” introduces a pan-African dimension to the critique, positioning migration not just as a Nigerian dilemma, but as a continental failure to build viable state systems. This expands the discourse of identity from national to racialised/global scales. At the discursive level, comment 24 depicts a larger social media pattern that transforms japa from simple physical movement into a transformative journey towards modernity and self-esteem. The statement positions migrants as capable actors while side-lining or deactivating other groups within the narrative. The comment promotes a new vision of Nigerian citizenship that shifts from national belonging to the ability to escape dysfunction. The concept of citizenship expands beyond territorial boundaries because it now depends on one’s strategic movement. To japa is, therefore, to claim not just a new location, but a new identity: that of the sensible, global Nigerian.

Tweet 4: “Japa: No future in Nigeria, nothing’ll make us return - UK-based couple”

Comment 25: “Nothing but the truth!! Those that are saying otherwise should wait till they have the opportunity. Nigeria drains and don’t wait till Nigeria happens to you.”

Comment 26: “You’re absolutely correct, there’s nothing in Nigeria. Nigeria is a Zoo a mirage, it’s irredeemable and nothing works in this Zoo call Nigeria. if you’re not happy with what I said go and hug the nearest Transformer.”

Comment 25 captures the cumulative trauma of existence in Nigeria. The use of metaphor like “Nigeria drains,” “Nigeria happens to you,” frames the country as an active, destructive force—personifying the state as a violent actor. Nigeria is constructed as a villain while the migrant is the victim. Discursively, this supports migration as a survival tactic rather than a betrayal. In a similar view, comment 26’s declaration of hopelessness, coupled with the aggressive challenge to dissenters, “go and hug the nearest Transformer,” highlights the intensity of affective disillusionment. These utterances reflect wider social practices of state delegitimation, reinforcing a diasporic identity that defines itself in opposition to the homeland. In a twist, homeland is identified not only as a physical reality but as an affective place as demonstrated comments below:

Comment 27: “If I travel out I will still come back to Nigeria. Nowhere like home, original place you come from.”

Comment 28: “What has the future of all those that japa in the 60s 70s 80s turned into, many are lost totally without any trace back home. Funny enough they abandon home. Goodluck to them, we are here doing the best for our fatherland.”

Textually, the phrase “original place” in comment 27, signals an attachment to the homeland. This presents Nigeria, not as a failed state, but as a root identity—For a discussion of ‘identity’, see Salmani Nodoushan (2013). The speaker is activated as a proud patriot whose identity is not undermined by economic migration. In a related but more critical voice, the speaker in comment 28 critiques the cultural amnesia and detachment often associated with long-term diaspora life. By excluding the conditions that led to earlier migrations, this speaker constructs migrants as morally compromised for abandoning “home.” Staying at home “doing the best for our country” discursively promotes heroism while framing citizens abroad as disconnected from communal continuity.

Comment 29: “Even NEPA no go miss you. Stay there and continue eating fish and chips. Here, we are enjoying suya and still fighting for generator supremacy.”

This sarcastic commentary uses humour to downplay the migrant's self-importance while ironically referencing the chronic infrastructural issues, like electricity, that fuel migration. Textually, it juxtaposes cultural pride (*suya*) with infrastructural decay (generator), thus discursively reinforcing national resilience. The speaker is activated as a self-aware patriot, enduring and ironically superior, while the migrant is passivated.

Comment 30: "Even the president has not stayed in Nigeria for a complete 30 days since swore in."

Comment 31: "Wait till they get some Ministerial or Political nominations... They will run back to grab it."

Comment 32: "But you are still not better than Dangote, Otedola and many other wonderful Nigerians."

The comments above highlight the hypocrisy of the elites and the emigrants as exemplified by comment 30 and 31. They are activated as opportunists who denounce Nigeria publicly, especially the migrant who in future will exploit the system is offered a position of power. Discursively, these users reflect a deep-seated distrust in political sincerity, extending public disillusionment to include Nigerians in diaspora. From the perspective of moral superiority and identity hierarchy, the speaker in comment 32 excludes systemic critique by invoking successful individuals—"Dangote," "Otedola,"—within Nigeria as counterexamples. It functions as a moral leveller, challenging the assumption that relocation implies superiority. This framing passivates the emigrant as one among many, thereby flattening their narrative into a generalised experience of personal choice, rather than structural necessity.

5. Discussion

This study examined the discursive construction of the *japa* phenomenon in Nigerian digital space, *X* (formerly *Twitter*), using critical discourse analysis to explore how language, representation, and platform dynamics shape evolving notions of citizenship. The findings show that digital narratives reframe migration as more than a socio-economic choice; it becomes a moral critique and symbolic act of exit from a broken national compact. Fairclough's three-dimensional framework enabled us to understand how text (lexical choices) combined with online discourse intertextuality and social context political disillusionment create an emotionally charged yet fragmented digital public. Through irony, sarcasm, metaphor, and narrative framing, *X* users cast 'japa' as a rational, even heroic form of resistance. Van Leeuwen's Social Actor theory further illustrates how commenters position themselves and others within binary oppositions. The commenters create divisions by labelling

themselves and others as patriots and deserters or survivors and hypocrites or hopefuls and cynics.

There is a persistent activation of political elites as agents of decay, while many Nigerians, especially the youth, are passivated as casualties of systemic failure. However, the discourse does not entirely dismiss those who stay behind. Patriotic citizens who choose to remain are often valorised in parallel as resilient actors committed to rebuilding from within, embodying an alternative civic imaginary that affirms presence as a form of resistance. Thus, citizenship is reimagined on dual fronts: both as exit (a refusal to consent to dysfunction), and as an enduring engagement. In sum, the findings show that 'japa' is not just a buzzword but a generative cultural discourse that challenges inherited meanings of belonging, voice, and nationhood. As discourse, 'japa' functions as a complex narrative where migration, patriotism, resistance, and citizenship are continuously negotiated.

6. Conclusion

The study examines the japa phenomenon within digital discourse, demonstrating the role of language and online interaction in shaping identity formation, critical reflection, and citizenship practices in modern Nigeria. Through daily exchanges on *X*, the research reveals that migration encompasses physical movement alongside discursive acts that express resistance and the redefinition of national identity. The research shows how online spaces serve as platforms for civic conversations where young people express their concerns and aspirations while challenging traditional Nigerian identity concepts. The japa phenomenon manifests as both a physical act and a narrative that holds meaning beyond escape, expressing demands for accountability, inclusion, and dignity.

Overall, the findings show that japa is discursively constructed as both critique and coping strategy within a context of perceived governance failure and socio-economic uncertainty. It is not only a migration trend but also a symbolic register through which Nigerians negotiate trust in the state, evaluate citizenship obligations, and articulate political disillusionment. The study further demonstrates that digital discourse on *X* functions as a participatory space where competing ideologies of patriotism, survival, and resistance are continuously produced and contested.

In conclusion, japa operates as a complex socio-discursive construct through which citizenship, belonging, and state legitimacy are renegotiated in digital space. The study contributes to understanding how online linguistic practices reflect broader ideological struggles over nationhood and identity in contemporary Nigeria.

Authors' Statement

Both authors contributed to the conceptualisation and development of the study. Isaiah Aluya was responsible for the introduction, theoretical framework, and methodology sections, while Nkechinyere U. Nwaegbe handled the data analysis, discussion of findings, and conclusion. Both authors jointly reviewed, edited, and approved the final version of the manuscript for submission.

The Authors

Isaiah Aluya (Email: Isaiah.aluya@binghamuni.edu.ng) is a Reader in the Department of English and Literary Studies, Bingham University, Karu, Nigeria, whose academic interests lie in English language and discourse studies. His research focuses on stylistics, discourse analysis, media representations of sociopolitical issues, and ecolinguistics. Over the past decade, his work has contributed significantly to discourse studies and applied linguistics, particularly in the areas of media narratives, political communication, and conflict discourse. His publications include studies on political apologies, farmers-herders conflicts, and cognitive stylistics in biblical discourse.

Nkechinyere U. Nwaegbe (email: nkechinyereuwaegbe@gmail.com) is a Nigerian doctoral researcher in English and discourse studies. Her research interests centre on discourse analysis, applied linguistics, and sociolinguistics, with particular focus on identity construction in discourse and the linguistic representation of sociocultural issues in contemporary communication. Her work explores how language constructs and mediates meaning across social and cultural contexts. She is undertaking her doctoral research in the Department of English and Literary Studies at Bingham University, Karu, Nigeria.

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